

ISic1480

I.Sicily inscription 1480

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary (?)

Material

sandstone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2008.09.28 (observed)

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Camarina

Place of origin (modern)

Kamarina

Provenance

Carnala, 5 km East

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Kamarina, Museo Archeologico
Regionale di Kamarina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI330700

1. ΔΥ [.] Λ,Ι,ΙΑΩΝ υἱὸς
2. Κόρυδος· με
3. Γέλων ἐποίησε.
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644990

EDCS 70900786

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Bibliography

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